

CHARACTERISTICS OF LINGUISTIC EXPRESSIVE MEANS IN MATT HAIG'S WORK "HOW TO STOP TIME"

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At present, the issue of expressiveness and expression is quite relevant. Expression is a characteristic feature of linguistic units regardless of their usage domain. The concept of expression is considered in various aspects such as lexicological, sociolinguistic, linguistic, linguostylistic, psycholinguistic, etc. The expressiveness of the text indicates emotional processes (sensory tone, emotions, affects, moods) that constantly accompany any human activity. Emotional processes, in turn, are a person's experience of his own attitude towards objects and phenomena of objective reality. This is one of the psychological mechanisms of specific regulation of human behaviour in the world. Scientists believe that the semantic and functional nature of expression manifests itself only in the process of the "life cycle" of the text, which includes such stages as "creation-text-understanding" or "conception-text-meaning." At the same time, expressive means directly influence the process of perception and understanding of the text by the recipient. They mobilize attention, focus it on expressively presented objects and phenomena, processes and events in the text, therefore, increase the intensity and stability of perception.

Keywords: expressiveness, expression, word-formation expression, phraseological expression, grammatical expression, phonetic and phonological expression.

In the linguistic literature, the most widespread classification of expression is based on the manner of its linguistic expression. This so-called tiered expression is realized through means of individual language levels, such as phonetic-phonological, morphological, lexical, phraseological, grammatical (morphological and syntactic) and textual levels.

Phraseological expression gives rise to phraseological units with a special usage. Vivid expression is created by individual transformations of phraseological units, i.e. violations of their semantic monolithicity. Phraseological units have different degrees of expressiveness. Units such as idioms, proverbs, sayings, winged expressions, etc., form a group of expressive and emotional phraseological expressions.

Word-formation expression is created through specific word-formation means, namely affixes, especially word-forming patterns and types.

Grammatical expression is created by the emotional and expressive potential of parts of speech, their categories and syntactic constructions. Textual expression arises within the broadest linguistic category – the text. One of its manifestations is found in the combination of the author's language and the language of characters.

The primary means of phonetic and phonological expression are phonetic tools. These tools include intonation and the play of sounds. The research is based on the works of Matt Haig. The author selected specific emotionally colored words that convey a particular situation or attitude towards it. Intonation is also present in the work, helps to grasp expressiveness and enhances speech clarity, taking into account the context. First of all, intonation in the work is reflected through punctuation marks such as commas, question marks and exclamation points. In other words, the construction of complex sentences, conveying dialogue, direct speech

requires accuracy in writing to understand the emotion the author wants to express through the characters.

In his works, Haig manages to depict intonation through the use of parallel constructions. In this example from the work, the repetition of the last phrase is illustrated. This technique is called epistrophe.

For instance: *"I am real! My life is real! This is very real!"*; *"Are you mad!"* (despite the sentence being constructed as a question, it is an exclamatory sentence spoken by the main character). The sentence is taken out of context; in the novel, there was a description of a conflict dialogue and this phrase is the last one in the conversation.

In the novel, there are also examples of intonation. For example: *"Quiet now!"* (there was an argument between the main character and his acquaintance; the fact that she raises her voice is evident from the exclamation mark and the context of the work); *"You're just stupid! It's completely nonsensical!"* (This is a continuation of the argument, but here the main character expresses aggression; this is indicated by the exclamation marks, the context of the work and the description of the events themselves).

The novel also includes many clichés, through which the author conveys expressiveness to the readers. Namely: *"You'll gonna be fine."* Such clichés are normal for everyday use among Americans and it is not unusual to address either a child or an adult using them.

The next phonological device is apheresis. Finding such a device of expressiveness is not so straightforward as in Haig's novels the language is quite clear and accurate, and his characters do not have any deviations in speech that would involve not pronouncing words correctly. This might be possible if the characters were slurring or stuttering.

It is necessary to note that these examples are taken out of context, so analyzing their correctness,

logic and adequacy is not necessary. Instead, attention should be focused solely on a specific technique that conveys expressiveness in the novels.

Morphological means are no less important for expressing expressiveness in any work, including films. They are expressed through gender, number, suffixes, prefixes, conveying a particular shade of a word. Additionally, morphological means include telescoping, abbreviation and contraction.

It is also worth noting that in the English language there is no gender distinction in professional titles to prevent discrimination against women. Therefore, neutral nominations are always used. In the Ukrainian language, such nuances do not exist, so it was highlighted during the reading of the novel: *"Is this doctor still here? She helped me in my situation. - She? Doctor woman?"*

It was found that in Haig's work, abbreviations and contractions were frequently used. Examples in the novel include *"old P.D.", "VIP", "Dr.", "UK"*. Throughout the novel, there was a prevalent use of commonly used contractions, typical in American everyday dialogue, such as *"mam", "dad", "gotcha", "im", "comin'", "talkin'"*. These are entirely typical and understandable for everyone.

The mentioned contractions and abbreviations are also preserved when translated into Ukrainian in the novel because they are typical, straightforward and understandable to all readers. Therefore, there is no need to fully translate or decipher them.

The author also frequently employs the degrees of comparison of adjectives as expressive means to enhance the impact of the narrative. The most commonly used suffix for this purpose is *"-er."* For example: *softer, grander, bigger, slower.*

Means of expressing expressiveness are also based on the lexical and contextual meanings of words. These include metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche and irony. Metaphor is one of the most productive means of enriching language and demonstrating linguistic economy. Its universality is evident in space and time, language structure and functioning. A simple metaphor is built on the similarity of objects by one characteristic. An extended or expanded metaphor consists of several metaphorical words that form a single image, complementing interrelated associative connections. This type of metaphor is characteristic of artistic style as its goal is to create ambiguity in the image. In Haig's work, there are examples like *"Snow flurries danced busily outside the window"* and *"I feel her eyes on the back of my neck."*

Metaphor is typically associated with the literary style of language, but it is also encountered in other functional styles due to the universality of its potential use. R. Hoffman, the author of several studies dedicated to metaphor, argued: *"Metaphor is purely practical. ... It can be applied as a tool of description and explanation in any field: in psychotherapeutic conversations and in discussions among airline pilots, in ritual dances and in programming language, in artistic education and in quantum mechanics. Metaphor, wherever we encounter it, always enriches the understanding of human actions, knowledge, and language."* [11, p. 327]

Metonymy is a figure of speech where the meaning of one word is transferred to the naming of another object associated with the first word by its nature. This expressive technique may seem similar to metaphor at first glance, but they should not be confused because metaphor is based on similarity, while metonymy is based on contiguity and associative connection. Examples in English include: *"the hall applauded"* (referring not to the physical space but to the audience present in the hall); *"the bucket has spilled"* (referring not to the bucket as an object, but to the water in it).

Cynecdoche is the use of a part of something to represent the whole or vice versa. For example: *"The White House announced that Joe Biden is running for reelection."* (Here, "The White House" is used to refer to the government or the President of the United States).

Irony is a way of expressing thoughts where a word or statement acquires a meaning opposite to its literal sense in the context. It involves mockery expressed through understatement and negation, presented in a form that gives the appearance of approval and agreement. The main purpose of irony is to create a humorous effect. Examples from the work include: *"She smiled a soft, troubled smile..."; "How clever it is!"* (*"Clever"* has a reversed meaning, implying *"stupid"*).

Means of expressing expressiveness also involve the juxtaposition of logical and emotional meanings. Exclamations are one of the lexical devices used for expressing expressiveness. Through exclamations, the speaker's feelings are conveyed, serving the function of emotional emphasis. Examples include: *"damn", "oh", "ha", "pff"*.

In English, as in other languages, the use of epithets is prevalent, creating stable combinations when specific definitions are employed. Over time, such combinations become idiomatic expressions. The primary stylistic function of an epithet is to reveal an individual evaluative attitude towards an object or idea, thereby making the language more vivid. Examples from the work *"How to Stop Time"* include: *mischievous dance, quizzical look, bewildered thing.*

In addition, among the main means of expression, stylistic devices such as stylistic figures (elliptical constructions, epiphora, anaphora, amplification, repetition, gradation, tautology, antithesis, asyndeton, parcelation, polysyndeton, leitmotif, pleonasm, rhetorical questions, question-answer, aposiopesis) and tropes (comparison, epithets, gradation, litotes, personification, hyperbole, allegory, periphrasis, irony, personification) can also be included.

Comparison is a literary device in which two concepts, objects or events are juxtaposed with each other, highlighting their distinctive features vividly. In English, comparison is often expressed using conjunctions such as *"as" "such as" "as if," "like" and "seem"*. The author provides examples like: *"the waves sound like breath", "the world is literally shrinking, like a balloon losing air", "her grey hair is as frail as dandelion seeds" and "the veins under her skin like routes on a secret map."*

Hyperbole is a device used to express emphasis through exaggeration. In this technique, two meanings are simultaneously conveyed: the primary, literal meaning of the word and the contextual, emotional meaning of the word. For example: "You have to match the hurricane." (This means that a person must confront challenges and cope with difficulties in life). "*I had been a ghost of myself...*"; "*I'm probably just like another dog for you to train.*" (This implies manipulation of a person).

The semantic gradation in the novel "How to Stop Time" illustrates the speaker's belief that innovations and innovative technologies do not emerge out of nothing but only arise under the condition of a qualitatively distinctive and unique experience of a particular person who can creatively utilize their own experience.

Expression can also be conveyed through expressive phraseological units. These include idioms, phraseological combinations and fixed expressions (proverbs, winged expressions, greeting phrases, etc., often extending beyond the limits of word combinations, i.e., forming sentences). An example of phraseological expressiveness could be the phrase: "*Poor Mary Peters. Mad as a box of frogs. Gets scared of TV.*" The idea of a box of frogs enhances the notion of chaos and unpredictability. The phraseological unit is used to describe a person or situation that seems absurd and illogical.

In this way, considering expressive elements on different linguistic levels, the following conclusion can be drawn: expression is inherent in language and manifests itself in the "disregard" of existing linguistic standards.

It is worth noting that the implementation of the expressive function of language is also aided by the context. The perception of context is a complex and multifaceted process, so the reader or listener must correctly understand the views, thoughts, feelings and emotions of the author, taking into account that any expressive statement represents the expression of a certain speaker's position relative to other communicants.

In the practical activities of humanity, a branched system of means of linguistic expression has been developed to implement the expressive function of language. This system is represented primarily by tropes and figures, which are designed to optimize communication and ensure a high degree of discourse influence on the recipient. It should be noted that expressively charged elements (expressives) can belong to various language units, regardless of their belonging to a specific linguistic system as repeatedly mentioned in the specialized literature.

The category of expressiveness is related to categories such as emotionality, stylistic coloration, intensity, imagery, connotation, aesthetic qualities, which need to be distinguished and not used interchangeably.

Expressiveness is one of the most polysemous categories in linguistics. It forms a complex relationship with categories such as emotionality, stylistic coloration, intensity and imagery. Within this framework, it is important to define how the concepts of expressiveness, emotionality and evaluation relate to each other. We have explored the scope of the terms expression, expressivization and expressiveness, influencing the way language functions.

The author frequently employs expressive means since expressiveness is a crucial component of the pragmatic category, vividly embodying its influential function. The main task of the speaker is to persuade and influence the audience's perception of information, which is one of the immediate objectives of the expressiveness category.

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